

UPWARDS

Deliverable D7.2

Reports with data from on and offline panels

WP	7	Public Participation
Task	7.2	Collect stakeholder data on noise, shadow flicker, risk and other social and environmental issues

Dissemination level¹	PU	Due delivery date	31/10/2021
Nature²	R	Actual delivery date	27/10/2021

Lead beneficiary	WUR
Contributing beneficiaries	ITWM, AWS, IVKDF

Document Version	Date	Author	Comments ³
1.0	Until August	Paula Struthoff, Helena Solman, Mattijs Smits	Paula worked as UPWARDS intern
1.1.	Until September	Helena Solman, Mattijs Smits, Sophie le Bras, Julien Christophe, Benjamin Adrian	
1.2 - Final version	Until October	Helena Solman, Mattijs Smits	

¹ Dissemination level: **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU), **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the JU), **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the JU)

² Nature of the deliverable: **R** = Report, **P** = Prototype, **D** = Demonstrator, **O** = Other

³ Creation, modification, final version for evaluation, revised version following evaluation, final

Deliverable abstract

Public concerns over wind energy are complex as they tend to be case-dependent and linked to personal or collective attitudes to wind and renewable energy. However, existing literature on the acceptance of wind energy has highlighted that the key concerns emerging across Europe tend to be linked to visual and auditive public perception of wind parks and how these impact local communities. Wind turbine noise is one of these recurring key concerns. In particular, the literature has documented that annoyance to wind turbine sounds affects public acceptance of new and existing wind parks. To address concerns about wind turbine noise, noise data can be internalised into wind turbine simulations. By doing so, noise concerns can be anticipated, and the simulation framework itself could be used to facilitate better decision-making about noise management strategies, and improved turbine design and operation.

The goal of this report is to demonstrate how UPWARDS simulation platform achieves that by integrating wind turbine noise data to provide guidelines for how noise perceptions (and linked to them data) should be understood within the socio-political context of wind energy in Europe. More specifically, this report shines light on how one of the objectives of UPWARDS, that is to predict wind turbine noise is achieved thanks to a numerical simulation platform developed in the framework of the project. The UPWARDS simulation framework could be used to facilitate better decision-making about noise expectations and turbine design and operation. For example, the simulation platform allows to adapt the threshold of annoyance to a certain db(A) level, depending on the local regulations. For this purpose, noise predictions have to be compared against noise annoyance and regulation criteria to determine if the sound levels are acceptable. This report identifies these criteria so that numerical simulations can be used as a tool for better wind energy governance.

By drawing on existing literature, this report identifies different levels of noise and linked to them degrees of acceptance. These noise levels span from 30dB(A), where little to no annoyance can be expected, to >45dB(A), where over half of the residents can be expected to report annoyance. We suggest placing an upper limit at 45dB(A) to minimise public disturbance due to noise in the simulation and list specific wind turbine noise regulations in Europe, which UPWARDS should account for. Whilst this presents a robust approach to predict levels of community acceptance to wind energy, we argue that noise annoyance alone may account for only some of the reasons for why local communities may resist wind energy. Other concerns, such as degree of financial involvement or the visual impacts on landscape are also likely to play a role. This is why we highlight the limitations of using noise simulation for predicting public support for and opposition to wind energy. Taking these into account, we provide examples for how the simulation can be applied as a tool of co-production in wind energy governance for future wind energy projects, beyond the UPWARDS simulation framework.

Highlights

- Wind energy developments are often opposed, with noise annoyance as a key concern and argument against wind energy
- This report identifies different levels of noise and linked to them degrees of acceptance. These noise levels span from 30dB(A), where little to no annoyance can be expected, to >45dB(A), where over half of the residents can be expected to report annoyance
- Noise annoyance can be linked to other societal concerns, including but not limited to visual impacts, financial participation and impact on wind life
- The physical simulation models can be used as a tool in governance to facilitate decision-making about design and management of new and existing wind parks

Deliverable Review

Reviewer #1: /Coordinator			Reviewer #2:		
Answer	Comments	Type *	Answer	Comments	Type *

1. Is the deliverable in accordance with

(i) The Description of Work?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(ii) The international State of the Art?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<i>Not applicable for this deliverable</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<i>Not applicable for this deliverable</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a

2. Is the quality of the deliverable in a status

(i) That allows it to be sent to European Commission?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(ii) That needs improvement of the writing by the originator of the deliverable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(iii) That needs further work by the Partners responsible for the deliverable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a

* Type of comments: M = Major comment; m = minor comment; a = advice

Table of contents

1. INTRODUCTION.....	4
2. SOCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS OF WIND ENERGY	7
3. METHODOLOGY	9
4. PUBLIC PERCEPTION OF WIND ENERGY NOISE: ANNOYANCE THRESHOLDS....	12
5. WIND TURBINE REGULATIONS IN EUROPE	17
6. DEMONSTRATING THE INTEGRATION INTO THE UPWARDS NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS	19
7. DISCUSSING SOCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS IN THE SIMULATION....	23
8. CONCLUSION.....	29
9. BIBLIOGRAPHY	30

1. Introduction

The erection of wind turbines and parks has been met with varying degrees of concern throughout Europe. Changes to landscape (Devine-Wright, 2005), noise complaints (Bakker et al., 2012), and the danger that wind turbines pose for bats and birds (Dai et al., 2015) are frequently mentioned societal concerns with respect to wind energy. The planning and construction of new wind parks needs to consider these social and environmental concerns in order to prevent opposition and to improve the environmental sustainability of wind energy developments.

This report presents an approach and specific data to integrate social and environmental aspects of wind energy into a digital simulation framework (also called a digital twin). It is the second part of the Horizon 2020 UPWARDS project's work package 7 (WP7). UPWARDS is an innovative, interdisciplinary European project striving for a more optimal design of wind turbines and wind-energy parks through an integrated simulation framework (also referred to as a digital twin). UPWARDS seeks to improve wind turbine technology by exploring the possibility of upscaling wind turbine size to 15 MW while considering both social and environmental factors. The purpose of this integration of social and environmental aspects of wind energy is to develop more socially salient wind turbines and wind parks. Therefore, UPWARDS aims to optimise the wind turbines for these social and environmental aspects from the conception stage onwards. This can be done such as by

limiting noise to accommodate public concerns in the simulation, based on findings from state-of-the-art academic literature.

The focus of this study is on sound emitted by wind turbines which is a source of environmental noise. Noise from wind turbines, identified in the previous report 7.1, is a significant concern for residents. UPWARDS strives to combine noise modelling with data from noise regulation in different European countries, on the basis of academic literature on the topic. To achieve this, we present a study of surveys conducted in Europe from the last two decades. In addition to noise, we elaborate on other social and environmental aspects to account for the complexity of factors linked to public acceptance of wind energy developments.

The methodology underlying this study is a mixed-method synthesis of published studies from multiple locations in Europe, including both quantitative and qualitative aspects of noise perceptions and acceptance. By taking this approach, it is possible to establish how to use social data to simulate noise and predict levels of public acceptance while taking into account other factors that may relate or go beyond noise concerns and affect their degree of acceptance. Doing so, this report shows how noise as a parameter of acceptance can be directly integrated into the UPWARDS simulation platform.

Objective and research questions

The objectives of this report are twofold: firstly, to provide direct input for the digital twin model for UPWARDS, focussing on noise, and secondly, to convey the complexity and interaction of social and environmental aspects of wind energy. This approach is to move from direct, specific input for the UPWARDS simulation to more general observations and suggestions for wind energy projects in general.

Three research questions guide this study:

1. What levels of noise can be identified as degrees of annoyance based on existing literature on acceptance of wind turbine noise in Europe?
2. What are the national regulations for wind turbine noise in Europe, as how do they compare to reported annoyance noise levels?
3. How can the platform of simulations such as the UPWARDS foster public engagement in decision-making about wind turbine design and management?

1.1. Overview of the report

It is the second report for WP7. The first report, 7.1 Literature review on social and environmental issues and acceptance of wind turbines provided findings to the research question of what societal concerns with respect to wind energy are present in Europe. This report builds on the findings of this research, as a second step on the way to integrating social and environmental aspects of wind energy into the UPWARDS project.

In chapter 2, we focus on public acceptance of wind energy, starting with a thesis that public engagement with matters of concern is central to resolving these concerns and improving overall acceptance of wind energy. In chapter 3, we outline the methodology of this report. Chapter 4 presents noise thresholds at which residents living close to wind turbines report annoyance. Chapter 5 presents and reflects on wind turbine noise regulations in Europe and comments on their implications for how these can provide boundary conditions for noise simulations in UPWARDS. Chapter 6 briefly illustrates how this existing data about noise annoyance and noise regulations in Europe can be integrated into the UPWARDS numerical simulations (digital twin). Chapter 7 contextualises and broadens the scope of the report by tying in other social and environmental aspects which contribute to public concerns over wind energy and are likely to interfere with reported noises annoyance by the public in practice. In doing so we reflect on the sensibility and limitations of quantifying noise related concerns (and possibly other social and environmental aspects of wind power) in order to explain/ predict public acceptance of wind energy. Finally, chapter 8 concludes the report and lays out next steps for WP7.

2. Social and environmental aspects of wind energy

In a previous report for work package 7 (D7.1) of UPWARDS, scientific literature has been reviewed in depth, discussing the social and environmental aspects of acceptance of wind power in Europe (Solman et al., 2020). We summarise the main findings here as these forms the foundation for this report.

The review lists and analyses multiple concerns, touching upon technical, social, environmental, and economic factors that can become a matter of public concern and in turn shape individual or collective attitudes towards wind power. The key aspects that can possibly be included in the simulation (based on what has been identified in report 7.1) or taken into account as important contextual factors are:

- Levels of annoyance caused by certain noise amplitude (can be directly integrated)
- National or regional regulations on noise (can be directly integrated)
- The influence of financial participation and revenue-sharing on acceptance (contextual)
- Levels of annoyance caused by shadow flicker
- Visual/aesthetic impact of wind power on landscapes
- Impact on birds and other wildlife

After detailed discussions with UPWARDS partners and modelling experts, it was decided to focus on the levels of annoyance caused by certain noise and on the national or regional regulations on noise to include in the simulation. Noise has been selected as a parameter that is well documented by the literature in relation to acceptance and corresponded with UPWARDS capabilities.

While acceptance and opposition are commonly used concepts to describe these attitudes in a binary form, there is an increasing recognition of that public attitudes toward wind power are dynamic (can change over time) and are complex (in that they are not always clear in terms of being for or against wind power). As a result, polarising attitudes as for or against wind power can be counterproductive as the literature on acceptance has argued that public engagement with and though emerging concerns is needed to continue on improving the sustainability of wind power and how publics can participate in design, planning and management of wind energy technologies and their landscapes.

The prior review of literature has also highlighted that matters of concern that are related to acceptance can be traced to individual people as well as groups of people, at local, regional, national or even transboundary level. These may also change over time and vary across the different stage

of wind turbine design, planning, implementation, and operation. This review shows that engagement with wind turbines goes beyond either accepting or opposing wind energy projects generally. It is context-specific and complex, which is why the common framing of opposition to wind energy developments as the main challenge and a major issue for governance of wind energy can be misleading (Solman et al., 2021).

Report 7.1 instead showed that the perspective of concerns rather than of factors of opposition offers a more fruitful way to understand what bothers people about wind energy landscape, technology, and the process of wind energy developments. Aiming to understand the concerns allows engagement with these at their root to create more socially robust wind turbines as is also the goal of the project. The UPWARDS simulation can do this to some extent, that is only to the extent that it is possible to obtain a model that accurately represents the multitude of public concerns related to wind turbine noise and how they may change over time. While it is relatively simple to link wind speed to noise (concerning for example validation data), linking noise and annoyance is more difficult, as it requires large survey studies, that should sample enough people for statistical convergence. Such studies exist; however, they tend to explain perceptions of residents related to noise at certain point in time, and longitudinal studies are less common (ref). A more novel approach is tracing how these attitudes change over time, and how they are affected by a range of local factors including landscape and weather conditions (DECO wind). Such sophisticated understanding of noise (that is supported by longitudinal or real time noise data) is however still lacking in the academic literature. This means that not all identified areas of noise concern can be included into the sophisticated integrated model that UPWARDS aims to deliver. This realisation is important as it makes clear what the possibilities and limitations of these models are and in turn how well the such modelling explains public acceptance of wind power.

This report is therefore overall a continuation of the previous report of work package 7. It reconciliates a critical approach to measuring perception of wind energy with an attempt to generalise some indicators of public perception for modelling within the integrated simulation, the goal of the UPWARDS project.

3. Methodology

The methodology of this study is developed to answer to each objective and research question; firstly, what levels of noise can be identified at which the public reports annoyance, secondly, what are national regulations and guidelines for wind turbine noise in Europe, and thirdly, how can the products of simulations such as the UPWARDS product be understood in relation to how public may respond to wind energy, critically reflecting on the simulation approach. It was imperative that the study could yield data that can directly feed into simulation, and it must also be able to provide a path to capturing the complexity of social challenges related to wind energy, which have been identified in the previous report.

To ensure this, two preliminary steps were taken to determine the foundation for the study more specifically. Firstly, all relevant partners from the UPWARDS project met to brainstorm and exchange. Thus, a group of social scientists from Wageningen University and Research, digital modelling experts from the Fraunhofer Institute, and noise modelling experts from Siemens and the von Karman Institute, debated what kind of social acceptability data would be needed. Here it was decided that the focus should be on noise data.

Noise thresholds in decibel (dB(A)) as ratio data at which the public perceives wind energy noise as annoying or bothersome was decided as the most appropriate measurement as this could be integrated into the model. dB(A) is a relative unit of measurements which is adjusted for audibility to the human ear, and commonly used in studies of perceived noise (Hansen et al., 2017). Overall radiated sound is used throughout the report (Alamir et al., 2021). The second step was a scoping of available studies to determine if this data format in the appropriate unit was available. A preliminary, scoping search of Scopus and Web of Science from basic searches (annoyance AND wind turbine noise, etc.) and reading of abstracts confirmed that.

After this discussion and scoping, it was concluded data from multiple studies in multiple locations in Europe would yield the most valid findings to meet our objectives, as it allows to cross-reference. This is because the UPWARDS numerical simulation platform could be used as a tool for design, planning and/or management of wind farm projects across countries in the future. Synthesising published work in such an approach has the advantage of integrating several empirical findings and perspectives to answer our research questions (Snyder, 2019). Given that the geographical area of interest to UPWARDS spans all of Europe, this approach also allows to draw on studies from multiple locations. The following chapter outlines how we operationalise this approach into a feasible research design.

Research Design Steps

In this section, we briefly outline the steps taken in designing and executing the study. Figure 1 shows an overview of the steps taken from problem identification to the write-up of this report.

1. Problem Identification	Integrating social and environmental aspects of wind energy in Europe into digital twin model
2. Study Development	Narrow down scope, research protocol with inclusion and exclusion criteria for studies, plan for data extraction and presentation
3. Method and Design Selection	Equal standing of qualitative and quantitative approach, not one leading (read texts for both)
4. Data Extraction	Check by second researcher, transparent reporting (tables with data)
5. Reporting and Discussion	Presentation of quantitative and qualitative elements and integration of both for value to UPWARDS project and beyond

Figure 1: Steps taken in developing the study

While we have covered step 1 in the introduction, step 2 entailed the determination of eligibility criteria for articles to be included in the study. For the quantitative understanding of noise concerns, we sought studies which measured public perception of wind turbine noise and on how noise correlates with other variables linked to acceptance. To gain a holistic understanding of noise concerns and the role they play in shaping public acceptance of wind power, we complemented these qualitative studies with selection of qualitative studies that provides insights on the complexity of noise concerns, based on expert recommendations and broad literature searches). These studies were included in the review if they had a geographic study area in Europe. Inclusion was also based on the availability of noise annoyance data and background information available to compare the findings to other studies. This included for example information about what kind of turbine's noise is used or simulated; what noise levels are included in dB(A) as the commonly used metric, as well as a usable metric for the digital twin. We also set a boundary for time of publishing of these studies to get up-to-date results. This boundary is set at 20 years hence we include studies ranging from 2001 to 2021.

To execute the search with the set criteria, step 3 entailed a search and sampling of studies that met the inclusion criteria. Firstly, we conducted a search in Scopus (modifications of search terms: ("wind turbine noise" OR "wind turbine sound" OR WTN OR "noise from wind turbine*" OR "turbine") AND (annoyance OR perception). We also reached out to several researcher centres and experts to obtain suitable studies on wind turbine noise (WTN) annoyance, resulting in four suitable studies on WTN for the European region.

For step 4 and 5, we carefully checked each other's extraction of data to avoid error and consulted experts from other UPWARDS work packages on the data, units, and reporting style to present a report that is both relevant for the UPWARDS simulation and for informing others who are generally interested in understanding how noise and noise modelling is relevant for understanding societal acceptance of wind energy.

4. Public perception of wind energy noise: annoyance thresholds

Noise annoyance in relation to wind farms can be complex to identify and analyse as there are different sources of sounds in wind farms that can cause annoyance. First, sound of wind turbine blades can be perceived as a noise and it is caused by the movement of the turbine's blades through the air (aerodynamic noise). A second kind of noise can be caused by the sound of the machinery (mechanical noise) of the turbine (Raman et al., 2016). Both sources can be a nuisance to residents living close by, who can perceive noise as more or less annoying, depending on factors such as terrain and weather. WTN can be perceived indoors and outdoors at residents' properties in vicinity of wind turbines, and while the levels of sound are one of the reasons for annoyance, the characteristics of this noise or a presence of particular tone can be perceived as annoying as well (Doolan, 2013). Similar to noise from car traffic, airplanes, or rail, WTN is often perceived as bothersome (Ellis & Ferraro, 2016) by people who are exposed to the sounds at their residences. WTN might however be a special case of environmental sound, as studies indicate that noise from wind turbines is perceived as more annoying than other common noise sources, such as noise from traffic/road noise (Schäffer et al., 2015). The thumping or swishing of the blades resulting in interrupted sound patterns and the particular tones emitted have been identified as the main noise source of annoyance (Klæboe & Sundfør, 2016; Palmer, 2017; Pedersen & Persson Waye, 2004). Studies have also surveyed perception of WTN at different noise levels (loudness), and have shown that at higher noise levels, high levels annoyance and resulting stress were recorded (Bakker et al., 2012; Schmidt & Klokke, 2014).

The World Health Organisation (WHO) therefore recommends that noise levels of wind turbines at residential areas do not exceed 45 dB(A) in Europe (World Health Organization, 2018). However, as annoyance below this upper limit of noise has also been reported, we consider WTN noise annoyance in more detail in this report. Minimising the noise disturbance from wind turbines is part of the UPWARDS project in its quest to design better wind turbines and wind park configurations. By integrating expected annoyance levels at different corresponding noise amplitudes, the UPWARDS simulation platform can optimise the overall model also based on annoyance. The underlying assumption for this is that annoyance increases with noise level when noticeable as studies suggest (Schäffer et al., 2015). The following sub-chapter analyses where approximated dB(A) noise thresholds might lie, which the simulation can then optimise for. The result is a scenario in which least amount of annoyance is made possible within limits of other modelling factors in the simulation.

4.1. Reported annoyance based on wind turbine noise: European surveys

We consolidate findings on annoyance at different noise levels in this chapter. Table 1 summarises data from studies on WTN perception from different European countries, chosen based on criteria outlined in the methodology chapter of this report.

The percentages shown in table 1 encompass reported annoyance levels from slightly annoyed to extremely/highly annoyed from the studies, where a comparable variation of a 5-point scale including 'not annoyed' was applied. Although the spread from 'slightly' to 'highly' annoyed is not detailed in these above-listed studies, we made note that at higher dB (A) intervals (over 40dB (A)), significantly more survey respondents were highly or extremely annoyed, where at lower dB (A) levels this option is hardly chosen by respondents (see studies cited in table 1). Comparing the percentage of residents annoyed at WTN at different dB (A) levels displayed in table 1, it is also of note that annoyance percentages in some cases do not increase with noise level. However, from comparing the data as this table does, generally for most cases it can be observed that the dose-response relationship holds, therefore we can derive rough expected levels of annoyance at different dB levels from these studies.

Table 1: Reported annoyance at wind turbine noise in Europe

Country	Key Data (% of sample annoyed at different dB levels ⁴)	Overall (% of sample annoyed at WTN outdoors)	Author	Survey	Turbines	Area	Distance
Netherlands	< 30dB(A) 4% 30-35dB(A) 19% 36-40dB(A) 41% 41-45dB(A) 52% >45dB(A) 66%	24%	Bakker et al. (2012)	725 survey responses	variety of wind turbines (different wattages)	different areas (rural to more urban)	2500m from WTs
Netherlands	<30dB(A) 4% 30-35dB(A) 17% 35-40dB(A) 38% 40-45dB(A) 42% >45dB(A) 34%	25%	Van Den Berg (2008)	725 survey responses	variety of wind turbines (different wattages)	different areas (rural to more urban)	2500m from WTs
Poland	<40dB 47.4% 40-45dB 44.4% >45dB 51%	46.4%	Pawlaczyk-Łuszczynska et al. (2018)	517 survey responses	mostly 2MW WTs	rural areas	up to 1700m from WTs
Sweden	<30dB (A) 0% 30-32.5dB (A) 14% 32.5-35dB (A) 35% 35-37.5dB(A) 38% 37.5-40dB(A) 51% >40dB(A) 56%	32.5%	Pedersen & Persson Waye (2004)	352 survey responses	smaller WT (600 kW, 650 kW, 500 kW, 150kW)	rural area	up to 1200m from WTs

Note: (1) The two studies from the Netherlands drew on the same data and performed their own analysis, hence the similar survey base. (2) The dB(A) level containers (2nd column) differ slightly between studies, as the studies consolidated in this table used varying dB categories.

⁴ dB levels at residences are mostly calculated in the reported-on studies, not measured, as precise measurements within the actual soundscapes are complex. However, calculated level aim to be slightly higher than actual at properties (Pohl et al., 2018), thus overcompensating, rather than underestimating the actual WTN levels.

4.2. Noise Annoyance Thresholds for the UPWARDS simulation

Based on the analysis of studies in 4.1, annoyance thresholds at different noise levels can be set for the purpose of integration into the digital simulation. We took the average of the value presented in Table 1 and further rounded them to the nearest dB(A) and percentages to make the table easier to interpret. We believe such a qualitative averaging is justified, given the differences between the studies and the qualitative nature of the problem.

Table 2 shows these for different decibel intervals, from WTN levels at which no or little annoyance can be expected to WTN levels at which a majority of residents can be expected to experience annoyance. The simulation model can integrate these thresholds to optimise for the least amount of expected annoyance under other optimisation factors, such as energy generation.

Table 2: Decibel thresholds at which level of annoyance can be expected

Sound level in dB(A)	Annoyance Response of Residents
<30	Not likely that residents perceive WTN as annoying (or perceive the noise overall)
30-35	Likely around 20% of residents will perceive WTN as annoying at this dB interval level
35-40	Likely around 40% of residents will perceive WTN as annoying at this dB interval level
40-45	Likely over 40% of residents will perceive WTN as annoying at this dB interval level
>45	Over half of the residents living in vicinity of WT report annoyance in all reviewed studies, hence a high annoyance response at this dB level is likely

Note: These are indications only as the results of several European studies (table 1) suggest as this format is useful for the UPWARDS simulation.

From table 2, we can interpret an upper level and significant changes in annoyance. As noise levels at <45dB(A) lead to high annoyance, the simulation could set an upper limit value for noise at 45dB(A). To check the validity of this upper limit assumption, we can corroborate with literature and policy guidelines. The WHO WTN guidelines for Europe also suggest a limit at 45dB(A). Furthermore, an in-depth study by Fredianelli et al. (2019) suggests an upper limit at 43.1dB(A), supporting our proposition for an upper limit around 45dB(A) maximum, based on expected annoyance for the UPWARDS project.

Table 2 also indicates a significant threshold for WTN over 35dB(A), after which expected levels of annoyance jump from 20% to 40%, presenting a large increase in reported annoyance. This suggests that another value of use for the UPWARDS simulation could be <35dB(A) as a value to strive for to keep expected annoyance levels of people living in vicinity of wind turbines low.

5. Wind turbine regulations in Europe

In addition to relying on existing literature that documents annoyance to wind turbine sound in the UPWARDS simulation platform, it is also useful to include wind turbine noise regulation (from now on just ‘regulation’) as a binding upper limit, which we briefly reflect on in this chapter. As an environmental noise source, WTN it is subject to regulation, which varies by country in the European region (World Health Organization, 2018). For some countries or regions, there is no specific noise limits set for WTN, but it is included in general noise limits. For others, there are specific regulations for WTN, further sub-divided into rural or urban area, and day or night-time (e.g., for Denmark)⁵. Whilst this regulation is not purely based on the annoyance potential of wind turbine noise, they can be a good guideline for what is too loud to limit public disturbance when planning or managing wind energy projects in the optimisation.

Researchers have reviewed and compared WTN regulation for different countries across the world (Alamir et al., 2021; Hansen et al., 2017; Koppen & Fowler, 2020), from which we can take the relevant regulations for Europe. As table 3 shows, specific WTN regulations are available for some European countries and regions.

Table 3: Wind Turbine Noise Regulation in Europe

European country (and region)	Setback Distance	Noise unit	Rural		Urban	
			Day	Night	Day	Night
Belgium (Wallonia)	Turbine height x 3	LAeq	45	45	45	45
Belgium (Flanders)	Blade length x 6	LAeq	48	43	44	39
Denmark	Turbine height x 4	LAeq	42–44	42–44	37–39	37–39
Denmark (indoors)	Turbine height x 4	LAeq, LF	25	20	25	20
Germany	N/A	LAeq	50	35	50	35
Finland	N/A	Laeq	45 (draft)	40 (draft)	45 (draft)	45 (draft)
France	N/A	LAeq	35	35	35	35
Italy	N/A	LAeq	50	40	55	45

⁵ <https://eng.mst.dk/air-noise-waste/noise/wind-turbines/wind-turbine-regulations/>

Ireland	N/A	LAeq	40	40	40	40
Norway	N/A	Lden	45	45	45	45
Switzerland	N/A	LAeq	50	40	50	40
Sweden	N/A	LAeq at 8 m/s	35	35	40	40
The Netherlands	N/A	Lnight	41	41	41	41
The Netherlands	N/A	Lden	47	47	47	47
United Kingdom	N/A	LA90	35–40	43	35–40	43

Note: LAeq is a unit related to dB(A), taking noise over time into account. Table adapted from Alamir et al., (2021); Hansen et al., (2017); Koppen & Fowler, (2020).

As can be observed, regulation is largely at or below 45dB(A), especially at night, however, in some cases such as for Germany it is above this threshold. Relating these regulations to our findings on expected annoyance, our recommendation for policy and for the UPWARDS simulation is to adhere closer to 35dB(A) limits, as a jump in reported annoyance occurs here, and staying below would likely result in significantly lower perceived annoyance.

The setback distance is a second regulatory criteria included in table 3 (second column) which is also related to the allowable noise levels. It denotes the regulated minimum distance between a wind turbine and residents that only some regions or countries have specified (Hansen et al., 2017). In the UPWARDS simulation platform, a minimum setback distance could be determined based on expected levels of noise, likely going beyond complying with regulatory minimums to optimise for social and environmental aspects of wind energy. This setback distance could help decision-makers (including private and public actors) determine where a new wind turbine should and should not be placed, in addition to other criteria in the selection process, such as terrain.

6. Demonstrating the integration into the UPWARDS numerical simulations

We have established that both a regulatory upper limit for wind turbine noise (WTN) and annoyance thresholds could be integrated into the UPWARDS digital simulation. In this chapter we briefly demonstrate how this can be done in the simulation. Figure 2 shows a noise map of the Hovsore wind turbine test site in Denmark, which has been used in the UPWARDS project as a basis for running acoustic numerical simulations. The wind turbine where sound is produced is indicated by a black cross. The figures below show the noise amplitude at the receiver locations at 1.5m above the ground, taking atmospheric and terrain effects into account. The noise predictions are computed accounting for terrain information and weather data (provisory for 1 hour in this demonstration). These noise predictions can be compared to expected annoyance levels and regulation levels in order to identify where areas of too much noise might lie, as we demonstrate here in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Hovsore test site noise propagation. Source: SISW and IVKDF (UPWARDS)

Given that UTM coordinates in figures 2 and 3 are in meters, the maps cover a radius of 1000m. Now, considering the upper limit of 45dB(A), residents would be expected to report high levels (around half likely to be annoyed) of annoyance at the noise within the area where noise is louder than this. Applying both this expected area of high annoyance from WTN, as well as regulation criteria, we get perimeters shown in figure 3.

Figure 3 Hovsore test site noise propagation with expected annoyance and regulation criteria as perimeters. Source: SISW (Siemens Industry Software NV) and IVKDF (von Karman Institute)

The black perimeter line corresponds to the region where sound from the central wind turbine is higher than 45dB(A), which we suggest as “too much noise” based on expected annoyance as discussed in chapter 4. In this case of the Hovsore site in Denmark, this line also approximately corresponds to the regulation for Denmark in rural areas, at $L_{Aeq} = 44$ dB. The purple inner perimeter shows the second regulatory criterion discussed in chapter 5, the setback distance, which corresponds for Denmark to four times the turbine height, approximately 320m for a Siemens 2.3 MW wind turbine as is on the test site.

More detailed results about noise annoyance are presented in figure 4 where the decibel thresholds at which level of annoyance can be expected are represented according to table 2.

Figure 4. Hovsore test site noise propagation with expected annoyance levels

With this information included in the simulation, UPWARDS can model both acoustic aspects of noise in a way that takes into account both regulation and annoyance data. One of the uses for the UPWARDS simulation might be as a consultation tool for decision-making over new wind park development projects. The addition of expected annoyance thresholds and regulations to the simulation may also help decision-makers (including e.g. experts, public and private actors) to deliberate about how noise in the wind farm area could be managed in each project context. While doing so, UPWARDS simulation platform could also enable to support their decisions with predictions that include the likelihood of annoyance response of residents within the noise propagation area. Applied to different sites, then, decision making regarding the building of new, or management of existing wind turbines and parks could be improved, for instance by identifying innovative strategies for preventing public disturbance already at the early stage of project design and planning, rather than later managing a negative response from residents disturbed by the wind turbines.

This demonstration shows a way of integrating some types of social data into numerical simulations which can lead to more socially robust designs of wind turbines and parks. If used in a transparent way, it could potentially open up decision-making over wind power developments to different types of actors. However, as noise concerns are complex, simulations like UPWARDS should be always

considered within a broader context of other factors that might play a role in how people respond to noise and what solutions and management strategies are deemed fair and acceptable. Based on literature, there are also other steps that could be taken in the further development of this simulation to further minimise public concerns over noise, such as simulating a lower rotational speed at night. However, little has been written in the academic literature about what impact this may have on annoyance. Nevertheless, it is possible to include a lowering of rotation speed of the turbines at night to anticipate annoyance levels, as doing so will likely lead to decreased annoyance of residents. Experts have argued that at night-time, people are more likely to be annoyed if they hear wind turbine noise (Van Den Berg, 2004). Highlighting this further point of possible integration in this demonstration chapter already points to the limitation of the simulation for the social concerns due to their complexity, which we discuss in more detail in the next chapter.

7. Discussing social and environmental aspects in the simulation

In this chapter we address the limitations of noise modelling within UPWARDS simulation platform in terms of the extent to which it can help decision-makers understand societal acceptance of wind energy. Then, we outline how the simulation could be used as a tool for public engagement. Doing so, we will show how other social and environmental issues and concerns may be intertwined with noise perceptions by the local public. The goal of this is to reflect on how digital twin technology, including simulation platform designed within UPWARDS can contribute to increased social, environmental and economic sustainability of wind energy technology and their integration in landscapes. This requires reflection on the conditions under which such simulation platform can foster better decision-making over how, where and by whom wind energy is design, developed and managed (as argued in the deliverable 7.1).

We argue in this discussion that although the inclusion of social and environmental criteria in the UPWARDS simulation is a useful step in opening up a process of design for more socially robust wind turbines, this may not be sufficient to fully capture (or prevent) all public concerns. That said, the simulation could be used in governance of wind energy projects, such as by using it as a tool for early involvement of the public in wind turbine or wind farm design. This gives the possibility to further limit public concerns and possibly prevent conflict of opposition. We do however argue that it might be important to provide space for opposition and new concerns to be added to the simulation platform in order to create an even more inclusive and collaborative space for decision-making.

In 7.1, we firstly discuss the complexity of interrelated social and environmental aspects, including perception of WTN, which shows the limitations of the approach taken in chapters 4-6. In 7.2, we consider the end goal of the UPWARDS project, the simulation tool, which could be used in future wind energy design, planning and management. As not all social and environmental aspects of wind energy identified in deliverable 7.1 could be translated into the simulation, we discuss how these can be considered in the development besides the use of the simulation to further internalise public concern into decision-making over wind energy.

7.1. Interaction of social and environmental concerns over wind turbines

In previous chapters, we have treated wind turbine noise as causing different degrees of annoyance, which in turn can be interpreted as a parameter of acceptance or opposition to wind energy developments at local level. The studies consulted, such as the survey by Pedersen and Persson

Waye (2004) for the Netherlands, analysed respondents' reported annoyance levels directly based on wind turbine sound levels. However, consulting both quantitative and qualitative studies on other wind energy related issues such as shadow flicker or impact on landscapes, these are potentially confounding variables which shape residents' annoyance response to wind turbine noise (WTN). Indeed, that there is a more complex relationship between annoyance and noise is well established in the literature (Michaud et al., 2016). We present some of these other variables moderating the annoyance response to WTN and wind turbines more generally beyond the noise they emit. In doing so, we reflect on the broader academic debate on acceptance and opposition to wind energy as a dichotomous conception, which has already been criticised based on a comprehensive literature review in deliverable 7.1 of this working group.

In chapter 4 noise from wind turbines was presented as one source of annoyance to residents living in the vicinity of wind turbines. Wind turbines are large constructions and have caused annoyance based on other factors besides noise, such shadow flicker and a perceived negative visual impact on landscape. These have shown to independently cause annoyance. More critically for the discussion of the limitations of the approach taken in this report, studies have also shown that these other social and environmental factors impact the level of annoyance reported for noise from wind turbines. Figure 4 shows this visually, underlining the complexity of the relationship between noise and annoyance.

Figure 5: Moderated relationship between WTN and annoyance

This is not to say that all reported annoyance at WTN can fully be explained by other factors, which would invalidate this approach taken in chapters 4-6. Rather it is to show that the particular context of each wind turbine is relevant to consider as they are always embedded in the social environment and local context. For the simulation this means that minimising sound emitted from wind turbines might not predict an equal drop in annoyance as expected were there are no other variables present.

As illustrated in figure 4, visual effects have been shown to influence reported WTN annoyance levels. Wind turbines present an alteration on landscape, which both surveys and experiments have shown to also influence perceived annoyance at the noise (Janssen et al., 2011; Pedersen & Larsman, 2008; Preis et al., 2015). The respondent's or participants who reported annoyance at WTN also were dissatisfied with the visual impact of wind turbine, such as Klæboe and Sundfør (2016) find in the case of a wind park in southern Sweden. Explaining these interactions or attempting to establish causality penetrates disciplines such as environmental psychology, showing the breadth and interdisciplinary of this topic of public perception of wind energy and annoyance. A second moderator in figure 4 is financial benefits. In chapter 4, we reported on the levels of annoyance at different WTN levels. Generally, an exposure-response relationship could be established: the higher the noise level, the more annoyance was reported. However, this relationship, such as for the Dutch case of van den Berg et al. (2008), did not hold for very high levels of noise. Why annoyance is sometimes lower than expected at high noise levels, so also the study discusses (ibid), can be better explained when considering financial benefits received by residents living in audible vicinity to wind turbines. Janssen et al. (2011) identified that survey respondents exposed to WTN who also received financial benefits reported very low, if any annoyance at the noise.

Financial involvement such as compensation has also been shown to increase support and a more positive attitude for wind energy projects more generally, likely then also influencing the annoyance response (Breukers & Wolsink, 2007; Devine-Wright, 2005). Also under this umbrella of financial benefits, a cost and benefit perspective can be assumed. Hirsh and Sovacool (2013) analyse how a sense of unfairness from perceived dissociated costs and benefits of wind energy can influence perception of wind energy: wind turbines are often in rural areas and the rural population sees that they carry the costs of wind energy, such as a noise and visual impacts, but do not get the benefits such as cheaper and cleaner energy locally.

The final moderator shown in figure 4 which illustrates the complexity of the noise and annoyance relationship is shadow flicker, which describes the moving shadows produced when the sun shines through a wind turbine and casts a shadow. Although shadow flicker is usually minimised through planning of wind turbine location, it does occur and is a cause of annoyance to those affected by the flickering light and shadow. Voicescu et al. (2016) find that annoyance at shadow flicker and annoyance at WTN are not independent, but rather that the latter explains much of the former (and vice versa).

The discussed annoyance at wind turbines, from annoyance at the noise to visual, financial, or shadow flicker annoyance responses or an interaction of these, so we argue, should not be seen as direct *explanations* for either acceptance of, or opposition to, wind energy. These are rather *indicators* for the perception of wind energy, which is what the simulation will be able to do for social and environmental aspects. However, including these is likely not sufficient to addressing the issues the public holds for wind energy. Shepherd et al. (2011), for example, argue that reported annoyance at noise or noise complaints might also lie in other conflicts, such as between developers and the community and thus depends on the local context. As has been argued in the previous deliverable 7.1, the broader debate on acceptance and opposition to wind energy as a general dichotomous conception should be questioned, as this discussion chapter on the complexity and interaction of variables shows. Rather, perception is case dependent and cannot be easily simulated.

7.2. Integrating social and environmental concerns into wind energy planning using simulations

The UPWARDS project is designing an improved wind turbine, the simulation of which can then also be used to plan wind parks throughout Europe. The simulation has complex technical capabilities such as for example reducing noise by simulating low noise blades, and these computational methods in wind energy have been highlighted for their potential in improving wind energy (Deshmukh et al., 2019). In this second part of the discussion, the potential application of the simulation in projects is discussed to highlight its potential from a social perspective.

One of the major obstacles to installations of wind parks and realisation of wind energy projects in Europe is often seen as the response of the public, such as local opposition campaigns (Kontogianni et al., 2014). An outcome of WP7 has been the insight that this understanding of public engagement with wind energy as either opposition or acceptance is inadequate. This is foundational to UPWARDS, as the projects social impact aim is to create more robust wind turbines, both technically *and* socially, and not to purely mitigate future public opposition to wind energy, seeking to get to the cause, not just treat the symptom.⁶ Therefore, rather than seeing the public reaction to wind energy as an obstacle, it is seen as an important aspect of the social context of wind energy, and as a motivation to make wind power more socially palatable, as Aitken (2010) also argues should be the charge of wind energy development.

⁶ <https://www.upwards-wind.eu/objectives/>

Considering this, the simulation can be used as a tool for creating improved wind parks throughout Europe in the governance of wind projects: however, it does not specify how and by whom it is used. In application, the simulation could for example indicate a 'red flag' in the project when run, when regulations are not followed to the simulated noise levels would indicate high levels of annoyance. This 'red flag' could then be used as a first sign that more attention needs to be paid to the social and environmental context of the project, prompting discussions and participation. Overall, the simulations indications for annoyance potential and regulation could therefore prompt further deliberation in a project over its social and environmental impact.

We identified that some aspects, such as general annoyance at WTN, can reasonably be integrated into the simulation. We conceit that this approach has its limitations, as WTN annoyance as one social aspect has also shown to be explained by other factors such as conflicts between developers and a community. Now, what cannot be integrated into the UPWARDS simulation at this moment still matters for the end use of it. Using the simulation in development meetings with the public, for example, could prove beneficial to improving public perception of the project. In addition to the measures taken to minimise annoyance through the simulation, the process of applying the simulation in wind energy project with members of the community could further bring down annoyance levels.

This touches upon participation of stakeholders, and the important question of how this could be done best – an issue that has been part of UPWARDS discussion as the simulation also includes stakeholder participation⁷. Solman et al. (2021), for example, propose to move away from top down 'planning' of wind energy, towards more collaborative process of decision-making in which concerns of the residents are taken into account at the early stage of project design. Such approach of 'co-production' opens up a more inclusive decision-making about wind energy design, planning and management and can increase sustainability of wind energy systems. Simulations such as from UPWARDS could use used in this effort. Co-producing projects at early stage could help to embed wind energy better in local communities and improve wind energy projects greatly by using publics as an asset:

“Underscoring the value of moving from energy ‘planning’ to energy co- production. That is, a shift from predetermining publics and their concerns and values in the planning phase of a

⁷ <https://www.upwards-wind.eu/deliverables/>, D8.4 for more information on stakeholder participation

wind energy project to continually engaging the concerns and values of diverse publics across the entire life span of a project.” (Solman et al., 2021, p.6)

The simulation could facilitate this co-production, serving for example as a tool that supports dialogue amongst all stakeholders, testing of limits and opportunities within which choices are made based on the simulation outputs. This conceptualisation of the simulation as a tool of co-production emphasises that the complexity of social and environmental aspects of wind energy also concerns process, not just content such as input for the creation of the simulation.

Framed this way, when concerns over wind energy are seen as an asset in the creation of more socially robust wind turbines, the simulation can be understood as a tool to facilitate public engagement with wind energy projects to better them. How and by whom this tool should be used to best address discussed social and environmental aspects in the process of governance has not yet been yet considered in the practice (that is in participatory processes related to wind energy), and as such UPWARDS has contributed a novel approach to wind energy design, planning and management. This is why, we recommend to continue on improving the design of simulation platform (both its interface as well as what data, models and concerns are included in the simulation) in order to better represent the dynamism of social and environmental aspects of wind energy and use the simulation as a tool for better decision making over wind energy, from the early stage of design until decommissioning.

8. Conclusion

In this report, the possibilities and limits of the digital simulation have been tested through the attempt to include data from on- and offline panels on social and environmental aspects of wind energy, specifically on wind turbine noise. It is commonly understood that models and simulations have the capability to model e.g., certain geographical and atmospheric conditions, but they may be less suitable to accurately model human behaviour, such as whether a wind project will be met with public opposition.

Nevertheless, we successfully included societal aspects related to wind turbine noise, firstly the annoyance at different wind turbine noise levels, and secondly regulation for different regions pertaining to noise and setback distance for wind turbines. We found that levels of noise exceeding 45dB(A) at residents' properties will likely result in high levels of annoyance and that noise levels under 35dB(A) will likely keep annoyance levels low. Regulation from different regions largely reflects these noise levels and can also be included in the simulation.

UPWARDS simulation platform can help to optimise wind turbines also for other social and environmental aspects, not all of which can reasonably be integrated into the UPWARDS simulation as we discussed, such as feelings of unfairness or conflict with developers. However, the simulation can still address these beyond the direct integration of social and environmental data by serving as a tool for wind energy governance.

Rather than modelling human behaviour in its complexity, the simulation in the case of noise annoyance presents an indicator of what public reaction could be expected and can be a basis of discussion and decision making. These indicators could for example act as a 'red flag'. In application, the simulation could indicate when regulations are not adhered to, or high annoyance can be expected with other model specifications. This 'red flag' could then highlight that more attention needs to be paid to the social and environmental context of the project, prompting the project to consider these and find solutions fitting to the project's context. This presents a shift away from the conception that public opposition to wind projects is an obstacle to be overcome ('how can we placate people?') to addressing the underlying reasons for opposing, which we deem a more promising approach to engage with concerns about and possible opposition to wind energy.

9. Bibliography

- Aitken, M. (2010). Why we still don't understand the social aspects of wind power: A critique of key assumptions within the literature. *Energy Policy*, 38(4), 1834–1841. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2009.11.060>
- Alamir, M. A., Hansen, K. L., & Catcheside, P. (2021). Penalties applied to wind farm noise: Current allowable limits, influencing factors, and their development. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 295, 126393. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126393>
- Bakker, R. H., Pedersen, E., van den Berg, G. P., Stewart, R. E., Lok, W., & Bouma, J. (2012). Impact of wind turbine sound on annoyance, self-reported sleep disturbance and psychological distress. *Science of the Total Environment*, 425, 42–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2012.03.005>
- Breukers, S., & Wolsink, M. (2007). Wind power implementation in changing institutional landscapes: An international comparison. *Energy Policy*, 35(5), 2737–2750. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2006.12.004>
- Dai, K., Bergot, A., Liang, C., Xiang, W. N., & Huang, Z. (2015). Environmental issues associated with wind energy - A review. *Renewable Energy*, 75, 911–921. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2014.10.074>
- Deshmukh, S., Bhattacharya, S., Jain, A., & Paul, A. R. (2019). Wind turbine noise and its mitigation techniques: A review. *Energy Procedia*, 160, 633–640. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2019.02.215>
- Devine-Wright, P. (2005). Beyond NIMBYism: Towards an integrated framework for understanding public perceptions of wind energy. *Wind Energy*, 8(2), 125–139. <https://doi.org/10.1002/we.124>
- Doolan, C. 2013. A review of wind turbine noise perception, annoyance and low frequency emission. *Wind Engineering*, 37, 97-104.
- Ellis, G., & Ferraro, G. (2016). The social acceptance of wind energy. In *JCR Science for Policy Report*. <https://doi.org/10.2789/696070>
- Fredianelli, L., Carpita, S., & Licitra, G. (2019). A procedure for deriving wind turbine noise limits by taking into account annoyance. *Science of the Total Environment*, 648, 728–736. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.08.107>
- Hansen, C. H., Doolan, C. J., & Hansen, K. L. (2017). *Wind Farm Noise : Wiley Series in Acoustics , Noise and Vibration : John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.*
- Hirsh, R. F., & Sovacool, B. K. (2013). Wind Turbines and Invisible Technology: Unarticulated Reasons for Local Opposition to Wind Energy. *Technology and Culture*, 54(4), 705–734.
- Janssen, S. A., Vos, H., Eisses, A. R., & Pedersen, E. (2011). A comparison between exposure-response

- relationships for wind turbine annoyance and annoyance due to other noise sources. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 130(6), 3746–3753. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.3653984>
- Klæboe, R., & Sundfør, H. B. (2016). Windmill noise annoyance, visual aesthetics, and attitudes towards renewable energy sources. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 13(8), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph13080746>
- Kontogianni, A., Tourkoulis, C., Skourtos, M., & Damigos, D. (2014). Planning globally, protesting locally: Patterns in community perceptions towards the installation of wind farms. *Renewable Energy*, 66, 170–177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2013.11.074>
- Koppen, E., & Fowler, K. (2020). International legislation for wind turbine noise. *Euronoise 2015*, 321–326.
- Leiren, M. D., Aakre, S., Linnerud, K., Julsrud, T. E., Di Nucci, M. R., & Krug, M. (2020). Community acceptance of wind energy developments: Experience from wind energy scarce regions in Europe. *Sustainability*, 12, 1754. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12051754>
- Michaud, D. S., Keith, S. E., Feder, K., Voicescu, S. A., Marro, L., Than, J., Guay, M., Bower, T., Denning, A., Lavigne, E., Whelan, C., Janssen, S. A., Leroux, T., & van den Berg, F. (2016). Personal and situational variables associated with wind turbine noise annoyance. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 139(3), 1455–1466. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.4942390>
- Palmer, W. K. G. (2017). Why Wind Turbine Sounds are Annoying , and Why it Matters. *IMedPub Journals - Global Environment, Health and Safety*, 1(2:12), 1–17. <https://www.imedpub.com/articles/why-wind-turbine-sounds-are-annoying-and-why-it-matters.php?aid=21093>
- Pawlaczyk-Łuszczynska, M., Zaborowski, K., Dudarewicz, A., Zamojska-Daniszewska, M., & Waszkowska, M. (2018). Response to noise emitted by wind farms in people living in nearby areas. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15081575>
- Pedersen, E., & Larsman, P. (2008). The impact of visual factors on noise annoyance among people living in the vicinity of wind turbines. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 28(4), 379–389. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2008.02.009>
- Pedersen, E., & Persson Waye, K. (2004). Perception and annoyance due to wind turbine noise—a dose–response relationship. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 116(6), 3460–3470. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.1815091>
- Pohl, J., Gabriel, J., & Hübner, G. (2018). Understanding stress effects of wind turbine noise – The integrated approach. *Energy Policy*, 112(June 2017), 119–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.10.007>
- Preis, A., Szychowska, M., Hafke-Dys, H., & Kocinski, J. (2015). The influence of visual information

- on assessment of wind turbine noise. *Euronoise 2015*. <https://doi.org/10.1260/1475-472X.12.4.349>
- Raman, G., Ramachandran, R. C., & Aldeman, M. R. (2016). A review of wind turbine noise measurements and regulations. *Wind Engineering*, 40(4), 319–342. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309524X16649080>
- Schäffer, B., Schlittmeier, S. J., Heutschi, K., Brink, M., Graf, R., Pieren, R., & Hellbrück, J. (2015). Annoyance potential of wind turbine noise compared to road traffic noise. *Euronoise 2015*, 309–314.
- Schmidt, J. H., & Klokke, M. (2014). Health effects related to wind turbine noise exposure: A systematic review. *PLoS ONE*, 9(12), 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0114183>
- Snyder, H. (2019). Literature review as a research methodology: An overview and guidelines. *Journal of Business Research*, 104(August), 333–339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.07.039>
- Solman, H., Smits, M., van Vliet, B., & Bush, S. (2021). Co-production in the wind energy sector: A systematic literature review of public engagement beyond invited stakeholder participation. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 72(April 2020), 101876. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101876>
- van den Berg, F., Pedersen, E., Bouma, J., & Bakker, R. (2008). *Visual and acoustic impact of wind turbine farms on residents - Final report. 044628*, 1–99.
- van den Berg, G. P. (2004). Effects of the wind profile at night on wind turbine sound. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 277(4–5), 955–970. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2003.09.050>
- Voicescu, S. A., Michaud, D. S., Feder, K., Marro, L., Than, J., Guay, M., Denning, A., Bower, T., van den Berg, F., Broner, N., & Lavigne, E. (2016). Estimating annoyance to calculated wind turbine shadow flicker is improved when variables associated with wind turbine noise exposure are considered. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 139(3), 1480–1492. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.4942403>
- World Health Organization. (2018). *Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region Executive Summary*. http://www.euro.who.int/__data/assets/pdf_file/0009/383922/noise-guidelines-exec-sum-eng.pdf
- Wright, P. D., & Wright, H. D. (2006). Social representations of intermittency and the shaping of public support for wind energy in the UK. *International Journal of Global Energy Issues*, 25(3/4), 243–256. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijgei.2006.008994>